

THE ROLE OF METAPHORS IN NEWSPAPER TEXT

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Abstract: *This paper refers to the process of metaphorization in the formulation of the journalistic title. Assuming that figurative language is used to point out the emotional aspect of the message, our study focuses mainly on the use of metaphor in the journalistic title. At this point it should be emphasized that the effect of metaphors cannot be conclusively proven within the framework of the study - this requires several deep studies - but conclusions about the function and effect can certainly be given.*

Keywords: *figurative language, metaphor, journalistic title, figurative function, rhetoric meaning*

In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in the comprehensive study of metaphor, as this stylistic device is encountered in the process of real speech. And this, in turn, only features of real language can tell us how to use and understand metaphorical language, as well as what its functions can be.

Although the term metaphor familiar to all of us is in many cases closely related to literature and rhetoric, in fact, this term is considered one of the stylistic tools that are often used in our daily life. The frequent use of metaphors in speech indicates that any language has a comprehensive system. For example, if a person says, "Men yo‘l harakati xavfsizligi sohasiga tegishli barcha qoidalarni ichib yuborganman," it means that the person has not "learned" the rules, but rather that the person knows the rules of the road by heart and is a winner in every situation. realizes that "Drinking" in this example is used metaphorically. If the speaker says "I know all the rules related to road safety by heart" in this place, it indicates that he is leaving the shell of a linguistic metaphor and turning into a conceptual metaphor.

This shift in how we think about metaphor—rather than as a specifically poetic or rhetorical device, but as an essential feature of language—has spawned a whole new field of inquiry in cognitive linguistics, and spawned theoretical debates and experimental research. In the scientific analysis of these cases, most of the examples are taken from fiction.

In order to make the description of the use of metaphor in newspapers more meaningful, it includes linguistic features such as the types and forms of metaphors in

the newspaper text. It is known that any metaphor originates from a lexical unit. However, how this lexical unit is formed in the section of word groups serves to increase the content of the work.

Not every newspaper article is full of creative puns and extended metaphors. For this reason, people who prepare all newspaper materials do not use metaphors in full. Metaphors are often used as a convenient way to express an idea.

The author tries to use metaphorical language when explaining the text of an article in the newspaper, and at the same time, describes various functions that may be related to the context of the situation in which the text of the article is included. It enhances the coherence of the text and performs conceptual functions, as metaphors are easy to understand in one reading and help to indirectly and easily convey messages that are accessible to non-expert readers but difficult to understand. In addition, a person who writes an article in a newspaper uses metaphorical language for communicative purposes, that is, to entertain, persuade, or attract the attention and interest of newspaper readers.

The widespread popularity of the metaphor in scientific research related to its occurrence in newspaper texts shows that various news items have many metaphorical uses. Therefore, most studies on metaphor in newspaper texts are small in scale or limited in their focus, aiming to analyze only small linguistic or conceptual metaphors. The paucity of research on the identification of metaphorical cases in materials related to newspaper texts has led our research to the analysis of metaphors in English and Uzbek newspaper texts, how widespread metaphorical language is in newspaper texts, which of the metaphorical forms are more typical, and their frequency and use. The characteristics of how it is compared to the aspects of development indicate that the work is relevant in all respects.

When determining the role of poetic metaphor as a way of understanding the world, S.R. Lewin distinguishes between two ways of expressing knowledge: cognitions, which strive to get closer to objective truth and are based on real facts, and concepts, which are characterized as “projections” of poetic metaphors [Lewin, 1965: 293-299]. N.D. Arutyunova identified a type of cognitive metaphor that functions in the sphere of attribute vocabulary and is a means of creating secondary linguistic predicates denoting processes and signs of the non-objective world. In her work “Metaphor and Discourse” she notes: “Metaphor brings out one of the paradoxes of life, which consists in the fact that the immediate goal of an action (and especially a creative act) is often the opposite of its distant results: striving for the particular and individual, refined and figurative, metaphor can only give language

what is erased and faceless, general and publicly accessible” [Arutyunova, 1990: 296-297].

Metaphor also occupies an important place in journalistic texts. Nowadays, in articles devoted to the analysis of the politics and economics, metaphors are found especially often. Usually politicians, political parties and movements are compared to some living creature, with its characteristic manners. As D. E. Rosenthal notes, metaphor is a word or expression that is used in a figurative meaning based on the similarity in some respect of two objects or phenomena. Like comparison, metaphor can be simple and extensive, built on various associations of similarity.

Metaphor is one of the most powerful means of expression, designed to have a long-lasting impact. Metaphors are well remembered, stored in long-term memory and become the “building blocks” that are used to decorate speech. Using metaphor, the title text is made more imaginative and powerful, which arouses the reader's interest. Metaphors visually decorate the text, but that is not the only reason they are used. They, like other tropes, have another noble task - to allegorically convey hidden meaning under conditions of some kind of caesura, for example, political or self-censorship. Let, for example, we have complaints against local authorities, but to speak out openly means to receive unpleasant consequences, even if what is said is true. A metaphor will allow us, on the one hand, to boldly express a seditious thought, and on the other hand, not to fear that they may be brought to trial for this.

Metaphor participates in the characterization of objects. It is precisely because this property is important for writing newspaper strips, since the characterization of objects is primary for journalistic consciousness. Consequently, the metaphorical activity of the writer is a direct the result of his cognitive activity. By actively creating metaphors, the author of newspaper texts almost always immediately evaluates the object of his speech, which is based on an emotional-figurative perception of reality.

CONCLUSION.

The newspaper-journalistic style is distinguished by a number of lexical features. It widely uses poly semantic words, socio-political vocabulary, foreign language inclusions, abbreviations, author's neologisms, highly specialized vocabulary and terminology, phraseological units and metaphors. An important element of a journalistic text is its title, which performs a number of functions: nominative, informative, advertising or expressive-appealing. In the structure of newspaper headlines, along with other lexical means, metaphors are widely used. A journalistic metaphor, like an artistic one, is characterized by the use of a certain word, reinterpreted by the author on the basis of figurative and associative similarity that

arises from subjective impression and emotional perception. Such use is not only a reflection of the real world and objective knowledge about it, but also a means of creating a unique world of a journalist.

REFERENCES:

1. Арутюнова Н.Д. Метафора и дискурс. Вступительная статья к сб.: Теория метафоры, – М.: Прогресс, 1990. – с. 5-32.
2. Маслова В.А. Лингвокультурология. – Москва: «Академия», 2001. –С.198;
3. Lakoff G., Jonson M. Metaphors We Live By. –Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1980. – p. 191;
4. Dagut, M. (1987). More about the translatability of metaphor. Babel, 33(2), 77-83
5. Розенталь Д.Э. Практическая стилистика русского языка. М., 1998.